

Low Circulating Free Triiodothyronine Levels are associated with the Progression of Diabetic Nephropathy in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes

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Abstract:

This study investigates the correlation between low levels of circulating free triiodothyronine (T3) and the advancement of diabetic nephropathy (DN) in individuals diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Over the course of a year, a study was carried out at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital in Patna. The study involved 150 patients with T2DM who were closely observed for any alterations in renal function and T3 levels. The study findings revealed a noteworthy connection between lower T3 levels and an elevated urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR), as well as a decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). These results suggest that reduced T3 levels may contribute to the accelerated progression of DN. The findings emphasise the importance of considering thyroid hormone status in the treatment of diabetic nephropathy. It is crucial to explore potential therapeutic strategies that focus on improving thyroid function.

Keywords: Diabetic nephropathy, Triiodothyronine, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Renal function

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Introduction

DN is a serious complication of T2DM and is a significant contributor to end-stage renal disease on a global scale [1]. The progressive nature of DN is characterised by the gradual decline in kidney function, which can result in significant health problems and higher expenses for medical care [2]. New research has shown that thyroid hormones, specifically triiodothyronine (T3), have a significant impact on kidney function and the way our bodies process glucose. T3, the active form of thyroid hormone, plays a crucial role in maintaining metabolic balance and has been linked to different aspects of diabetic complications [3,4]. There have been observations of low circulating levels of free triiodothyronine in patients with T2DM, indicating a possible connection between thyroid hormone status and the progression of DN [5].

Nevertheless, the exact correlation between decreased T3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy is still uncertain. The objective of this study is to examine the link between decreased levels of circulating free triiodothyronine and the advancement of diabetic nephropathy in individuals diagnosed with type 2 diabetes [6]. The study aims to improve our understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms behind DN and

potentially discover new biomarkers for early detection and management of this condition [7,8].

Methodology

This study was a prospective observational study conducted over one year at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), Patna.

Study Population: The study included 150 patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) who met the criteria for diabetic nephropathy (DN). Participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria:

- Confirmed diagnosis of T2DM.
- Age between 40 and 70 years.
- Presence of diabetic nephropathy, indicated by elevated urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR) or reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR).

The Exclusion Criteria Were:

- Pre-existing thyroid disorders.
- Other chronic kidney diseases.
- Current use of thyroid hormone replacement therapy.

Baseline Assessments

At the onset of the study, baseline assessments were performed, which included:

- Measurement of circulating free triiodothyronine (T3) levels.
- Evaluation of kidney function through serum creatinine and UACR.
- Comprehensive metabolic profile.

Follow-Up and Data Collection

Participants were followed for one year with regular check-ups, which included:

- Periodic measurement of free T3 levels.
- Monitoring of renal function parameters (serum creatinine, UACR, and GFR).
- Clinical evaluations to track the progression of DN.

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted to evaluate the correlation between low free T3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy. The primary outcome measures were changes in UACR and GFR over the study period. The data were analyzed to determine whether low T3 levels were associated with a more rapid progression of DN.

Results

The study included a group of 150 patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), with an average age of 58 years. The majority of the individuals were male, comprising 65% of the total, while the remaining 35% were female. The baseline characteristics showed that most participants had moderate to severe diabetic nephropathy, with high urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR) and low glomerular

filtration rate (GFR). At the start of the study, the average level of circulating free triiodothyronine (T3) among participants was 1.2 ng/dL (± 0.3 ng/dL). The assessments of kidney function revealed an average UACR of 450 mg/g (± 150 mg/g) and an average GFR of 55 mL/min/1.73 m² (± 12 mL/min/1.73 m²).

During the one-year follow-up period, the average levels of free T3 among participants showed a decrease to 1.0 ng/dL (± 0.4 ng/dL). Notable changes were observed in the progression of diabetic nephropathy during this period.

- The average UACR rose from 450 mg/g to 600 mg/g (± 180 mg/g), suggesting a decline in kidney function.

- The average GFR showed a decrease from 55 mL/min/1.73 m² to 45 mL/min/1.73 m² (± 14 mL/min/1.73 m²), indicating a decline in renal function.

A significant correlation was found between low free T3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy, as indicated by the statistical analysis. There was a strong negative correlation (-0.62 , $p < 0.01$) between changes in T3 levels and UACR, and a strong positive correlation (0.68 , $p < 0.01$) between changes in T3 levels and GFR. These findings indicate that decreased T3 levels were linked to an accelerated advancement of nephropathy. Based on the findings, it appears that individuals with type 2 diabetes who have low levels of circulating free triiodothyronine may experience the advancement of diabetic nephropathy. There appears to be a connection between lower T3 levels, increased UACR, and decreased GFR. This suggests that the status of thyroid hormones might contribute to the decline in kidney function among this group.

Parameter	Baseline (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Follow-Up (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Change	p-value
Circulating Free T3 (ng/dL)	1.2 $\pm$ 0.3	1.0 $\pm$ 0.4	-0.2 ng/dL	<0.01
Urinary Albumin-to-Creatinine Ratio (mg/g)	450 $\pm$ 150	600 $\pm$ 180	+150 mg/g	<0.01
Glomerular Filtration Rate (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	55 $\pm$ 12	45 $\pm$ 14	-10 mL/min/1.73 m ²	<0.01

Correlation Analysis:

Parameter	Correlation Coefficient	p-value
T3 Levels vs. UACR	-0.62	<0.01
T3 Levels vs. GFR	0.68	<0.01

This table provides a clear overview of the changes in key parameters and their statistical significance over the study period.

Discussion

This study highlights a strong link between low levels of circulating free triiodothyronine (T3) and the advancement of diabetic nephropathy (DN) in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [9]. During the one-year follow-up period, there was a significant decrease in free T3 levels. Additionally, there was a decline in renal function, indicated by an increase in the urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR) and a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) [10,11]. A strong correlation was found between lower T3 levels and the deterioration of DN, as evidenced by the significant associations observed with both UACR and GFR. Based on the findings, it appears that a decrease in free T3 levels could potentially play a role in the progression of diabetic nephropathy. This could be attributed to the impact of free T3 on metabolic regulation and renal function [12].

This study offers new perspectives on the impact of low T3 levels on the progression of DN in T2DM patients, shedding light on the significance of thyroid hormones in renal health and glucose metabolism, as previous research has already emphasised. [13] The correlation between the rise in UACR and the decline in GFR in individuals with lower T3 levels suggests a potential link between thyroid dysfunction and the worsening of diabetic kidney disease. This discovery aligns with previous research indicating that thyroid hormones have an impact on the functioning of the kidneys and the flow of blood within them. It is believed that this influence may be due to processes involving inflammation and fibrosis.

The findings of this study have significant implications for clinical practice, indicating that closely monitoring and potentially intervening in thyroid hormone levels may have a positive impact on slowing down the progression of diabetic nephropathy [15]. Additional investigation is required to delve into the fundamental processes through which low T3 levels impact kidney function and to evaluate whether interventions aimed at regulating thyroid hormone levels could provide therapeutic advantages in the management of diabetic nephropathy. In conclusion, this study contributes to the increasing amount of evidence that connects thyroid function with complications in individuals with type 2 diabetes. It emphasises the importance of adopting a comprehensive approach when it comes to managing patients with this condition.

Conclusion

The findings of this study suggest a strong link between decreased levels of free triiodothyronine (T3) in the bloodstream and the advancement of diabetic nephropathy (DN) in individuals diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM).

There was a noticeable decline in T3 levels over the course of one year, which was found to be associated with a deterioration in renal function. This was evident from the rise in urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR) and the decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). These findings indicate that lower T3 levels could play a part in the progression of DN, emphasising the importance of thyroid hormone status in diabetic kidney disease. Additional research is needed to delve into the underlying mechanisms of this connection and assess the viability of thyroid hormone management as a potential therapeutic approach for preventing or alleviating diabetic nephropathy.

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